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Finger Reader: a Wearable Technology for Visually Impaired

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a project coming out of MIT that makes use of a small camera inside slightly oversized ring housing. It satisfy its output to software that can identify the words, and then speak them loud to the user in real time. Blind or otherwise visually disabled people can now read books without reading to learn Braille, to learn a new language, we require each day practice. Small, vibrating motors insisted in the ring whir to life to notify the user if his or her finger should stay too far away from the target text and when they reach the end of a line of text. Such authorizing functionality in such a portable form factor is sure to have a variety of applications apart from our standard leisure reading.

Keywords : Assistive device; Text reading; Wearable camera; Finger worn interface; plasticine

1. INTRODUCTION

In MIT's Media Lab, developers shirkott, Huber and others are working on the Finger Reader a ring-like device that fold itself around your finger and reads printed text out loud with a electronic voice, thanks to a mounted camera and strongly modified open source software.

The Finger Reader's voice is clipped and metallic – what one might liken to a Berlitz tape speaking through clenched teeth – but it is something the Finger Reader team is aware of and is working on among many other things. The finger reader is plasticine and upon first-hand check rules, weights no more than a regular ring. We hear the words loud, keep the finger on text which you need to read. It has a small camera on top of the ring.

It will not work with content as small as, like on a medicine bottle or baseball box scores, 12-point printed text it can be read, the on-screen computer component highlighting each word to the sound of what Shilkrot described as “bings and beeps.” Separated far from a line and a dial tone-like interrupt increases. If we remain on the line we can find the text . And though – as a whole – the Finger Reader sounds like a ‘Reading Pen’ Huber and Shilkrot differentiate it from the Pen which could be read, noting that it gives real time experience,in which the Reading Pen does not, and the software can read a line at a time and not word at time as is the case with a Reading Pen.

2. WHAT IS FINGER READER?

Finger Reader is a device that assists visually disabled users with text which could be read or words. It’s basically a ring the user wears on their index finger that contains a tiny camera and some hepatic actuators for feedback. When a visually disabled person wants to read some text then it maybe a card used in business, a menu card in hotel, a sign, they point their finger at the surface with The text and the device which read the words very loud. They can go fast, slow, go back, etc, and get feedback if they are wearing off a line of text making their finger back in the right direction.[1]

3. RELATED WORK

Giving VI people the ability to read printed text has been a topic of keen interest in academia and industry for the better part of the last century.[2] The earliest attainable evidence of an contact the text-reading device for the blind is the Optophone from 1914; however the more notable effort from the mid 20th century is the Optacon, a steerable miniature camera that controls a tactile display. In table I present a comparison of recent methods for text-reading for the VI based on key features: adaptation. For less-than-perfect imaging, target text, UI tailored for the VI and method of evaluation. we found a general presumption that the goal is to consume an entire block of text at once, while our effort focus on local text and gives the option of skimming over the text as well as reading it thoroughly. It also handles non-planar and non-uniformly lit surfaces gracefully for the same reason.

Of locality, and provide truly real-time feedback. Prior work presents much of the background on finger worn devices for general public use although in this paper we focus on a wearable reading device for the VI (visually impaired). Assistive mobile text reading products Academic effort is scarcely the only work in this space of assistive technology, with end-user products readily available. As smartphones became today’s personal devices, the VI adopted them, among other things, as assistive text-reading devices with applications such as the kNFB kReader Blind sight’s Text Detective. Naturally, specialized devices yet exist, such as ABiSee’s EyePal ROL, however interestingly;[3] the scene of wearable assistive devices is rapidly growing, with OrCam’s assistive eyeglasses leading the charge.

4. IS THIS THE END OF BRAILLE?

We do not think so, since there is much more to do and perfect before it can be reliable compared to Braille. In future years, when many of problems are resolved and VI people can rely on this technology to be strong, some may no longer need to learn Braille as they could use regular printed text. Not all Visually disabled people know Braille to begin with, only 9%, and actually many Visually disabled people manage regular hardcopy of books and large prints. Braille still makes sense, especially for Books and also in situations where the user does not want to hear the words spoken out loud (personal matter, health matters). But many magazine and other texts are not currently available in Braille: Only a fraction of books exists in Braille format. In order, events like letters, memos, reports, magazines, etc do not and will not likely to exist in Braille. One of the main values of the finger reader is that it makes a many content accessed to the blind in an immediate and real time way[4].

Publication	year	Interface	Target	Feedback	Adaptation	Evaluation	Reported	Accuracy
ezaki et al	2004	PDA	signage			ICDAR 2003 P	0.56 R	0.70
Mattar et al	2005	Head-worn	Signage		Color, Clutter	Dataset	P? R	0.901
Hanif and Prevost	2007	Glasses, Tactile	Signage	43-196s		ICDAR 2003 P	0.71 R	0.64
SYPOLE	2007	PDA	Products, Book cover	10-30s	Warping, Lighting	VI users	P 0.98	R 0.901
Pazio et al	2007		Signage		Slanted text	ICDAR 2003		
Yi and Tian	2012	Glasses	Signage, Products	1.5s	Coloring	VI users	P 0.68 R	0.54
Shen and Coughlan	2012	PDA, Tactile	Signage	<1s		VI users		
Kane et al.	2013	Stationery	Printed page	Interactivity	Warping	VI users		

Table 1: Recent efforts in academia of text-reading solutions for the VI. Accuracy is in precision (P) recall (R) form, as reported by the authors. This report is of the OCR / text extraction engine alone and not the complete system.

5. FINGER READER: A WEARABLE READING DEVICE

Finger Reader is an index-finger wearable device that supports the VI in reading printed text by scanning with the finger. The design continues work we have done on the Eye Ring however this work features novel hardware and software that includes hepatic response, video-processing algorithms and deferent output modalities. The finger-worn design helps focus the camera. The ring prototypes at a fixed distance and utilizes the sense of touch when scanning the surface. Additionally, the device does not have many buttons or parts in order to provide a simple interface for users and easily orient the device.[5]

6. HOW DID THE IDEA COME ABOUT?

Research lab at the MIT Media Lab is focused on developing more natural user communication receiver. By that we mean devices that are more of a natural extension of people and their behaviors. The thought of wearing a camera on your index finger would make for a natural information receiver, because people naturally point at things to ask questions about what's around them. About 2.8% of the population has a visual problems, and the solutions they use right now for reading text are far from optimal. The opinion of giving them a wearable device that is quicker to use and gives them real time feedback would make their lives easier[6].

7. HARDWARE DETAILS

The Finger Reader hardware expands on the Eye Ring by adding multimodal message through vibrate motor, a new dual-material case design and a high power mini video camera.[7] Two vibrate motors are embedded on the top and bottom of the ring to provide sense of touch feedback on which direction the user should move the camera via distinctive signals. The dual material design provides flexibility to the ring's fit as well as helps to feel strong the vibrations and reduce confusion for the user. Early tests showed that users preferred signals with different patterns, e.g. pulsing, rather than vibrating different motors, because it is easy.[8]

8. SOFTWARE DETAILS

To accompany the hardware, we developed a software stack that includes a text extraction algorithm, hardware control driver, integration layer with Tesseract OCR and Flite Text-to-Speech (TTS) currently in a standalone PC application. The text-extraction algorithm expects an input of a close-up view of printed text. We start with image binarization and selective contour extraction.[9] Thereafter we look for text lines by fitting lines to triplets of pruned contours; we then prune for lines with feasible slopes. We look for supporting contours to the candidate lines based on distance from the line and then eliminate duplicates using a 2D histogram of slope and intercept. Lastly, we refine line equations based on their supporting contours. We extract words from characters along the selected text line and send them to the OCR engine.[10] High confidence words with high are retained and tracked as the user scans the line. For tracking we use template matching, utilizing image patches of the words, which we accumulate with each frame. We record the motion of the user to predict where the word patches might appear next in order to

use a smaller search region. When the user veers from the scan line, it react to have sense of touch and audible feedback. When the system cannot find more word blocks along the line we touch an event to let users know they reached the end of the printed line. New high-confidence words incur an event and invoke the TTS engine to emphasize the word loud. [11]When skim the users hear one or two words that are currently under their finger and can decide whether to keep reading or move to another area. We focused on runtime efficiency, and usually frame processing time on our machine is within 20ms, which is suitable for real-time processing. Low running time is important to support randomly skimming text as well as for feedback; for the user gets an immediate response once a text region is detected.

© Ring Type

9. WORKING OF FINGER READER

The latest whiz bang gizmo from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's Media Lab, the same technology and design group which introduces Sixth Sense, is called Finger Reader. It is a tool both for visually disable people that require help with reaching printed text, which is an aid for language translation. users scan a text line with their finger and receive an audio feedback of the words and a hepatic feedback of the layout: start and end of line, new line, and other cues. [12]The Finger Reader algorithm knows to detect and give feedback when the user veers away from the baseline of the text, and helps them maintain a straight detection motion within the line. And it could be a landmark device for helping blind people or those with visual challenges read without braille. A small camera positioned on the top of the ring carefully detect the text. when the user moves their finger across the text, a electronic voice reads the words loudly, quickly translating the text from any printed material including books, newspapers and restaurant menus. [13]The developers created a software program which could tracks the finger's movements and identify the word and it will process , that information for the voice recognition start to read aloud.when the users separated from the correct order of the text the vibration motor alerting the reader that their finger has gone off course.[14]

10. ADVANTAGES OF FINGER READER

- a) The device is simple.
- b) It has a set of vibrating sensors, which alert you when you separate from the line and when you reach the end of a line.
- c) Finger Reader picks up words immediately.
- d) The device is used in every context in which people find themselves reading: restaurants, hospitals, at work, around the house.
- e) It is more flexible.
- f) visually disabled persons but also
- g) The elders, children, language learners and tourists.

11. WHAT IS THE FUTURE OF WEARABLE TECH?

It is clear that today's personal devices such as tablets and phones are very noisy in their use. Lot of research have been done in these days both in academia and in industry on more natural user interfaces that give us more obvious join access to digital information and services while we are going about doing other things. We suspect in the future years we will see a lot more wearable devices such as glasses, bracelets and watch enabling us to see some relevant information without running into a telephone pole or getting into an accident.[15]

12. WHAT UPGRADES IMPROVEMENTS DOES THE FINGER READER NEED?

Make it faster, good in performance, smaller in order to learn applications for people without visual problems.

13. WHAT IS THE ESTIMATE OF THE MARKET SIZE FOR THIS TYPE OF DEVICE?

Almost 3% of the population is visually disabled, so that is the market size for the Finger Reader. But other side we think it has potential to assist not only visually disabled persons but also the elders, children, language learners and tourists.[16][17]

CONCLUSION:

The reading ability which we take it in indifferent manner but up until recently it's also something that's difficult for millions of visually disabled people. The Finger Reader makes us to change the people those with disabled eyesight read regular books and text without to solve difficulty for Braille.

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